

On clp-paracompact spaces

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Abstract. The clp-paracompact spaces were defined and studied by A. Sondore. These spaces are those such that each clopen cover of them has a locally finite clopen refinement. Then, these spaces are related to ultraparacompact and to clp-compact spaces. In this paper, we obtain a theorem showing that every clp-paracompact Hausdorff space is the image of a clp-paracompact zero-dimensional Hausdorff space for a clopen continuous map with clp-compact fibers.

1. Introduction

SONDORE and ŠOSTAK [5] defined clp-compact spaces and related these spaces with compact, connected and zero-dimensional spaces. They also studied some properties of clp-compact spaces (e.g., products, countability). Afterwards, SONDORE [6] defined clp-paracompact spaces, and studied some properties of them (for example, their preservation for preimages of clopen maps with clp-compact fibers).

On the other hand, there exist various early results [1]–[4] on the existence of zero-dimensional paracompact spaces and perfect maps onto certain spaces (metric, paracompact, etc.). These results allow us to reduce the study of these spaces to those of them that are zero-dimensional.

In this paper, we prove that each clp-paracompact Hausdorff space is the image of a clp-paracompact zero-dimensional Hausdorff space for a clopen continuous map with clp-compact fiber.

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First, we list some previous definitions:

Definition 1 ([5]). A topological space is clp-compact if each clopen cover contains a finite subcover.

Definition 2 ([6]). A topological space is clp-paracompact if each clopen cover has a locally finite clopen refinement.

Definition 3. A map f between two spaces X and Y is clopen if the image for f of each clopen set of X is a clopen set of Y .

2. Main results

Theorem 1. *Let X be a clp-paracompact Hausdorff space. Then there exists a clp-paracompact Hausdorff topological space X^* with $\dim X^* = 0$ and a clopen continuous map f from X^* onto X such that $f^{-1}(x)$ is clp-compact for every point $x \in X$.*

PROOF. Let $\mathcal{F}_\lambda = \{F_\alpha \mid \alpha \in A_\lambda\}$ be a locally finite clopen covering of X , and $\{\mathcal{F}_\lambda \mid \lambda \in \Lambda\}$ be the family of all locally finite clopen coverings of X . Let

$$X^* = \left\{ \alpha = (\alpha_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} A_\lambda \mid A_\lambda \text{ discrete topological spaces such that } \bigcap_{\lambda \in \Lambda} F_{\alpha_\lambda} \neq \emptyset \right\}.$$

If $\bigcap_{\lambda \in \Lambda} F_{\alpha_\lambda} \neq \emptyset$, then it is a point.

Let $f : X^* \rightarrow X$ be the map $f(\alpha) = \bigcap_{\lambda \in \Lambda} F_{\pi_\lambda(\alpha)}$, where π_λ is the projection

from $\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} A_\lambda$ onto A_λ . Clearly, f is continuous and onto.

We prove that f is clopen: Let B be a non-empty clopen subset of X^* . We have that $f(B)$ is closed by [2, Th. 2]. For each $x \in f(B)$, there exists $\alpha \in B$ such that $f(\alpha) = x$ and a base member $\bigcap_{\lambda \in F} \pi_\lambda^{-1}(\alpha_\lambda) \subset B$ (with F finite and

contained in Λ) such that $\alpha \in \bigcap_{\lambda \in F} \pi_\lambda^{-1}(\alpha_\lambda)$.

Then $x \in f\left(\bigcap_{\lambda \in F} \pi_\lambda^{-1}(\alpha_\lambda)\right) \subset f(B)$, thus $x \in f\left(\bigcap_{\lambda \in F} \pi_\lambda^{-1}(\alpha_\lambda)\right) \subset \bigcap_{\lambda \in F} F_{\alpha_\lambda} \subset f(B)$. Since $\bigcap_{\lambda \in F} F_{\alpha_\lambda}$ is an open set, we have that $f(B)$ is open in X .

Moreover, $f^{-1}(x) = \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} B_\lambda$, with B_λ finite (for every $\lambda \in \Lambda$), then $f^{-1}(x)$ is compact (and clp-compact).

Finally, we will show that X^* is a clp-paracompact Hausdorff space with $\dim X^* = 0$. Let \mathcal{U} be an arbitrary clopen covering of X^* , then \mathcal{U} can be refined by a family \mathcal{B} of clopen sets. Since $f^{-1}(x)$ is compact for any $x \in X$, there exists a finite subfamily $V_{x,1}, \dots, V_{x,n(x)} \in \mathcal{B}$ such that $f^{-1}(x) \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{n(x)} V_{x,i} = W_x$, which is a clopen set also. If $D(x) = X \setminus f(X^* \setminus W_x)$, it is also clopen and there exists a $\lambda_0 \in \Lambda$ such that \mathcal{F}_{λ_0} refines $\{D(x) \mid x \in X\}$. Since

- (a) $\{\pi_{\lambda_0}^{-1}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in A_{\lambda_0}\}$ refines $\{f^{-1}(D(x)) \mid x \in X\}$;
- b) the order of $\{\pi_{\lambda_0}^{-1}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in A_{\lambda_0}\}$ is 1,

we have (by transfinite induction on $x \in X$) that there is a clopen covering $\{U_x \mid x \in X\}$ of order 1 with $U_x \subset W_x$, for every $x \in X$. Let

$$\mathcal{V} = \left\{ U_x \cap (V_{x,i} \setminus \bigcup_{j \leq i} V_{x,j}) \mid i = 2, \dots, n(x), x \in X \right\}.$$

Then \mathcal{V} is a clopen covering of X^* , of order 1, which refines \mathcal{U} . Thus X^* is a clp-paracompact Hausdorff space with $\dim X^* = 0$. □

Proposition 1. *Let (X, T) be a topological space. Then (X, T) is clp-paracompact if and only if each clopen covering of (X, T) has a σ -locally finite clopen refinement.*

PROOF. For each clopen covering \mathcal{U} of (X, T) , there exists a clopen refinement $\mathcal{V} = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \mathcal{V}_n$ such that \mathcal{V}_n is locally finite (for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$). If we call $V_n = \bigcup_{V \in \mathcal{V}_n} V$ and $W_n = V_n \setminus \bigcup_{m \leq n} V_m$, then $\mathcal{A} = \{W_n \cap V \mid n \in \mathbb{N}, V \in \mathcal{V}_n\}$ is a locally finite clopen refinement of \mathcal{U} . □

References

- [1] K. MORITA, A condition for the metrizability of topological spaces and for n -dimensionality, *Sci. Rep. Tokyo Kyoiku Daigaku Ser. A* **5** (1955), 33–36.
- [2] K. NAGAMI, A note on Hausdorff spaces with the star-finite property. II, *Proc. Japan Acad.* **37** (1961), 189–192.
- [3] K. NAGAMI, A note on Hausdorff spaces with the star-finite property. III, *Proc. Japan Acad.* **37** (1961), 356–357.

- [4] V. PONOMAREV, Normal spaces as images of zero-dimensional spaces, *Dokl. Acad. Nauk SSSR* **132** (1960), 1269–1272 (in *Russian*).
- [5] A. SONDORE and A. ŠOSTAK, On clp-compact and countably clp-compact spaces, In: Mathematics, Latv. Univ. Zinât. Raksti, Vol. **595**, *Latv. Univ., Riga*, 1994, 123–142.
- [6] A. SONDORE, On clp-Lindelöf and clp-paracompact spaces In: Mathematics, Latv. Univ. Zinât. Raksti, Vol. **595**, *Latv. Univ., Riga*, 1994, 143–156.

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